

TOWARDS AN ACCELERATED NONLINEAR SOLUTION METHOD INSPIRED BY MULTISCALE AND MULTIGRID METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Numerical modelling of nonlinear behavior in composites represents a significant computational challenge, which this paper seeks to address. We are developing a family of numerical methods capable of efficiently and accurately solving general nonlinear multiscale problems. The essential components of the method are described along with possible future variations. The results of a preliminary implementation of the basic method are shown for simple linear and nonlinear elasticity. These demonstrate the capability of this approach to produce fine scale results in a scalable fashion.

1 INTRODUCTION

All engineered structures exhibit structural variation across length scales. Material structures at small length scales lead to emergent responses at larger length scales, which complicates modeling the behavior of a material without experimentally testing the response at the relevant length scale. Composite materials exacerbate this challenge by extending the range of possible variation due to the multiple constituents, which simultaneously offers many potential advantages for material design. The phenomenon of progressive failure introduces additional unique challenges as failure modes at small scales eventually coalesce to form a dominant crack at a larger length scale, bridging length scales as failure evolves. These challenges have motivated significant effort towards the development of multiscale modeling methods that each aim to strike a particular balance between computational efficiency, which favors modeling at coarser scales, and accuracy, which favors modeling at finer scales.

One collection of popular approaches are the various homogenization and homogenization-adjacent methods, which tend toward computational efficiency over local fine scale accuracy. While these can vary in the details, from asymptotic perturbation approaches [1] to variational techniques [2] to other simplifying assumptions [3, 4], the underlying principle is that the microstructure has sufficient regularity, typically periodic or statistically periodic, that one can consider a small number of local microscale problems, which are generally regarded as infinitesimal compared to the macroscopic domain. Regardless of the specific method, the responses from these microscale problems are then used to determine effective macroscopic properties, with each local problem contributing to the properties of a specific subset of the domain. These models are effective within the assumptions about periodicity and scale separation, such as in a unidirectional fiber composite sheet under loads well within the elastic regime. They can even accommodate moderate deviations from these assumptions, and with further model complexity, their applicability can be extended [1, 3, 5]. However, their effectiveness significantly diminishes when these fundamental assumptions are entirely violated. This limitation is particularly evident in phenomena like discrete fracture, where highly localized fine-scale details and their macroscopic effects pose a significant challenge for homogenization methods.

On the other side of the spectrum are methods which still produce a global fine scale solution but use various techniques to try to accelerate that solution over just directly solving on a global fine mesh. These techniques include domain decomposition [6, 7], multigrid methods [8, 9], and the MsFEM approach [10, 11, 12]. In the first, subdomain problems are alternated with the global problem, while in the second, coarser representations of the problem are alternated with the fine scale representation. In

both cases, the goal is to save effort on the global fine problem, making progress with other, faster alternatives and somehow incorporating that progress into the global fine solution. The third case does not alternate but instead produces a full set of multiscale basis functions on a relatively coarse grid, which are determined using local solutions on a much finer grid. This frontloads a large amount of effort on a finer grid, but the later solution process involves much fewer degrees of freedom (DoFs), despite a solution with nominally fine grid resolution. While there are technical difficulties that must be addressed in all these cases, especially around discontinuities and nonlinearity, and these methods will in general require more effort than a homogenizing approach, the fact that these methods produce a global fine solution is appealing for complex geometries where the fine detail of the stress and strain is potentially critical anywhere in the component.

A third class of methods are global-local methods, which in some sense combine features of the previous two classes. For much of the domain, a relatively coarse, typically homogenized, method is applied, while at specific regions of interest, typically geometric features like corners and holes which induce stress concentration, a much finer method, possibly just a direct solve on a fully resolved grid, is used [13]. This is feasible as it involves only a smaller portion of the domain. The fine scale solve is then incorporated into the global domain, involving additive error correction, basis enrichment [14] (similar to MsFEM but with a specific solution rather than a general fine basis), or a connection between the fine and coarse solutions through boundary conditions along the fine-coarse boundary. The key to these methods is generally that the fine scale problem is only tackled on small portions of the domain, and hence the effort is minimized while still producing fine detail at the regions of interest.

However, as geometries and microstructures grow both more complex and defy length scale separation, it becomes difficult to determine the location of critical stress concentrations *a priori*. In the most challenging cases, stress concentrations and eventually fracture initiation can form across much of the domain, rendering the traditional global-local ideas irrelevant. In this paper, we describe a method which is applicable to fracture in complex aperiodic geometries, requiring the capability to produce a solution at the finest scale. The method presented combines concepts from multigrid techniques and global-local methods to produce a method that is adapted for efficiency in nonlinear problems and flexibility for a variety of material models.

2 METHODOLOGY

Our proposed method broadly takes the structure of a multigrid method, with the displacement field solved on a hierarchy of meshes of different characteristic sizes, and with corrections passed between them. Nonlinearity is addressed primarily by formulating the coarse grid correction in terms of the Full Approximation Scheme (FAS), in which the right-hand side of the coarsened equations receives a correction term relative to just the coarsening of the original right-hand side. Briefly, given a fine displacement field at iteration n , u_n^f , with residual function r^f , the coarse problem to solve is $r^c(u^c) = r^c(P u_n^f) - P r^f(u_n^f)$, where r^c is a suitably defined coarse residual and P is the matrix that maps from a vector on the fine mesh to the corresponding vector on the coarse mesh. The FAS correction is the two terms on the right side, rather than just solving $r^c(u^c) = 0$. Approximately solving this coarser problem hopefully smooths the longer wavelength error components, and the result is used to correct the fine problem, with $u_{n+1}^f = u_n^f + Q(u^c - P u_n^f)$ where Q is the matrix which maps a coarse vector to its corresponding fine vector. The definitions of r^c, P, Q are what characterize the specific multigrid approach and are discussed below, with particular focus on ensuring that the computational cost of r^c scales appropriately with the mesh size for a nonlinear problem.

The primary distinguishing feature in our approach is the extensive incorporation of operations on an overlapping set of patches covering the domain into the operators r^c, P , and Q . By performing patch-local operations, and blending the results across the overlap regions, globally consistent fields can be obtained without needing to handle globally sized arrays, while also easing parallelism of the method. It also should allow for some degree of adaptivity in the future, where computation is only required for patches where nonlinearity is evolving while leaving the remaining patches unmodified.

Figure 1: Schematic showing the functional links between patch and global meshes (large and small squares), coarse and fine meshes (left and right sides), and displacements and residuals (bottom and top squares). Blue and red arrows indicate chains of functions over which are autodifferentiated. Green arrows (or arrows with green dashes) are the functions which are composed into the global coarsening and refining maps.

In order to work effectively with unstructured meshes at each scale, none of which necessarily nest with each other, we define our grid transfer operations in terms of L^2 projections between the Finite Element spaces on the respective meshes. Such non-nested meshes greatly increase flexibility in mesh generation while still allowing for each mesh to conform to the features which are present at that scale, so it was important to be able to handle them. However, since a projection defined on the entire domain would quickly become computationally intractable, involving the inversion of a fine-mesh-sized mass matrix $M_{ij}^f = \int \phi^i \phi^j dV$, we instead use projections restricted to the aforementioned patches, which collectively cover the entire domain. The resulting patch projections can then be smoothly blended into a global result. The diagonal and horizontal arrows in green in Figure 1 illustrate the component operations of the overall P and Q (right to left and left to right respectively): splitting from a global array to a collection of patch arrays, projecting the patch arrays, and reassembling the patch arrays into a single global array. Note that we omitted any arrows for refining of the residual, as that is not something required in multigrid. One factor that must be kept in mind with non-nested meshes is the potential for issues along the boundary. When a coarse element barely intersects the fine domain, projection of the “ghost” nodes outside the domain will be poorly conditioned. We are continuing to explore more rigorous bounds on when this ill-conditioning will prevent or impair convergence, but provided the grids are chosen appropriately, it can be mitigated.

The remaining operator to define is the coarse residual. Since for nonlinear problems, the constant re-evaluation of a Galerkin coarse residual $r_g^c(\cdot) = P r^f(Q \cdot)$ is as expensive as re-evaluating the fine residual itself, even slightly more expensive with the projections, we required a faster approximation. Note that there is no such issue for linear problems, as the coarse matrix can be evaluated once, with subsequent matrix-vector products only involving coarse-mesh-sized arrays. The key is a residual which does not directly invoke the fine problem, and its fine-mesh-sized operations. Our solution was to locally expand this residual as a Taylor series around the current reference displacement, then store the first couple of Taylor coefficient arrays instead. These can be used for a few iterations of nonlinear smoothing, converging towards the zero of the truncated residual, before moving the solver iterations to another scale, eventually returning with an improved reference displacement about which to recompute the coefficient arrays. This still provides meaningful progress towards the exact solution, at a much lower computational cost, before moving to the next scale. Note that the general principle of a multigrid method is that at each scale a portion of the error is smoothed, and the progress is passed either up or down to smooth a different portion of the error. As the reference displacement converges towards the solution, the accuracy of the root of this truncated residual improves, and hence we can still attain similar

accuracy to the case where we had used the Galerkin residual throughout the process.

A further improvement in speed is possible by performing the Taylor expansion on individual patches and blending the resulting patch residuals into a global residual. While this introduces inaccuracy along the patch boundary nodes, by applying the blending weights to these patch residuals at the fine scale before projecting back, in the “Patch Galerkin” residual whose derivatives are being examined, the resulting errant nodes receive a weight of zero, so accuracy is comparable to the globally computed coefficients. Additionally, the global Jacobian in this approach, while never explicitly formed due to the use of matrix-free global solvers, is markedly sparser due to the coupling of nodes only within patches and more amenable to parallelization. Figure 1 illustrates this patch-wise Taylor coefficient breakdown, with coefficients computed based on the derivatives along the red path and then used for residual evaluation along the blue path. Currently, we are leveraging the automatic differentiation abilities of the JAX library both to automatically compute and cache the derivatives along the red path, as well as to obtain Jacobian-vector products along the blue path for use in a matrix-free solver.

While effort on the coarse mesh dramatically reduces the effort required on the fine mesh, the final component of our proposed method addresses the fact that a multigrid method benefits from smoothing the fine error on the fine mesh. Operating on the entire fine domain is not cheap, but working on each patch independently at the fine scale will in general require less effort, since it scales linearly with the number of patches. Importantly, when applying a smoother at the fine scale, the solution on a patch will likely be inaccurate near the patch boundary, since the solution is fixed based on the solution projected from the coarse scale to ensure well-posedness. However, since the various patch results are blended to obtain the global fine solution, where the edges of each patch receive blending weights of zero, these inaccurate values along patch boundaries contribute little to the resulting fine-scale displacement field. Moreover, by cycling between patch-level iterations at the fine scale and iterative corrections at the coarse scale, according to the principle of multigrid methods, the solution along the boundary of patches at the fine scale improve with each cycle. We will show in the next section that such a cyclic approach can achieve errors well below that of just the coarse grid, while not yet as accurate as a global fine solution. The technique is partly inspired by the GFEM^{el} technique of Duarte et al [15, 14], although that method was applied only to specific subsets of the domain and incorporated the fine information as a basis enrichment rather than a multigrid correction.

The approach laid out above forms the foundation for a family of patch-based multigrid approaches that we foresee exploring in the future. We could more directly adapt the GFEM^{el} approach by using the patch solutions as basis enrichment functions. The method could be made at least partly adaptive, with fine scale computational effort only done on those patches in which the coarse solution changed by some threshold. The approach also opens many questions, such as the choice of which scales to act on patch-wise and which to handle as a single global domain or decisions about tradeoffs around the number of iterations on each scale. We will explore these questions and more variations in the future as the general technique is applied to larger, more complex problems.

3 RESULTS

The current implementation of proposed method has not been optimized, so the discussion here will focus on the error convergence performance both on a per-iteration and limiting basis, but we expect that effort on the coarse scale will reduce fine scale effort such that the total time is reduced. This should especially be true as the problem begins to scale up, which given the lack of optimization is not something that has been done at this point. For a rough idea, in the nonlinear sample problem below both the fine scale smoothing across all patches and solving the global coarse problem using already-computed Taylor coefficients took on the order of 30ms, while a global fine scale solution took on the order of 2 seconds. Computing the coefficients is currently the bottleneck, taking multiple seconds as well. However, these times are based on a single CPU, whereas the eventual plan is to work on GPUs, which is straightforward in JAX and which will greatly improve the efficiency of the autodifferentiation. It should also be emphasized that coefficient computation time scales primarily with patch size, which can be fixed independent of problem size, whereas the time for a direct fine scale solve scales with domain size.

The following examples consider an elastic body with nonuniform material properties. Body force

and boundary conditions were imposed to produce a known non-constant solution, and the displacement field was initialized to a zero solution on both the fine and coarse scales. The fine mesh was composed of 1054 linear triangle elements tiling a rhomboid shape, while the coarse mesh was a structured grid of 113 regular quadrilateral elements that covers the fine domain. The meshes were divided into 9 overlapping patches in a 3 by 3 layout. Figure 2 shows the global meshes on the left, with the overlapping bands highlighted in green. On the right, both meshes are split out onto individual patches, illustrating the boundary mismatch between the two.

Figure 2: Trial problem mesh structure for coarse (left) and fine (middle) meshes. Green bands denote the overlap regions between neighboring patches. Individual patches are shown on the right.

Dirichlet boundary conditions were enforced directly in the residual function through the Taylor coefficients, and consequently, the coarse mesh received no explicit boundary conditions. However, boundary conditions were explicitly imposed on the fine solution after every fine update. Figure 3 shows the magnitude of the constructed exact solution used in the following problems alongside its coarse projection.

Figure 3 Manufactured fine grid solution (left) and the patch-wise projection onto the coarser grid (right) using the patches shown in Figure 2

3.1 Solving Exclusively on the Coarse Mesh

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the L^2 error of a linear elastic and geometrically nonlinear elastic problem solved only on the coarser grid, with the only fine mesh action being implicit in the re-computing of Taylor coefficients periodically. Each odd tick on the x-axis corresponds to a global solve on the coarse mesh. For the nonlinear case, that involved four Newton iterations using one set of Taylor coefficients, while for the linear case a single use of a direct solver suffices. In both cases, the required linear system solves were done to machine precision. Each even tick on the x-axis denotes an update of the Taylor coefficients, which in the linear case amounts to changing the right-hand side of the FAS equation since the higher order coefficients are constant.

Figure 4: Error and residual convergence for linear (left) and nonlinear (right) elastic materials, alternating coarse iterations with coefficient updates.

The horizontal line in black for the error indicates the “coarsening error”, that is $\|Pu_{ex}^f - u_{ex}^f\|_2$. Since in a multigrid FAS cycle, the coarse solution will converge to Pu_{ex}^f , this is in some sense the best case for the coarse solution, and indeed the error of the coarse solution against the fine bottoms out there. However, even though we are at no point solving the fine problem, just using these coarse updates and imposing the Dirichlet conditions is sufficient to produce a fine solution that is slightly more accurate. This is further illustrated by the first few pairs of steps in the third plot, which separates the error specifically on interior nodes. It should also be pointed out that the coarse residual is not actually oscillating between multiple orders of magnitude. Since each even step updates the coefficients, we are using a new, theoretically more accurate, residual function on the same coarse displacement, and thus seeing some of the remaining error in the coarse solution.

Figure 5: Error and residual convergence for linear (left) and nonlinear (right) elastic materials, alternating coarse iterations with fine patch iterations.

3.2 Incorporating a Smoother on Fine Scale Patches

In the previous section, solves are only performed on the coarse mesh using the projected Taylor coefficients from the fine mesh, but in this section, we illustrate the effect of alternating between coarse scale solutions and fine patch smoothing for the same two problems. Figure 5 shows the error and residual information as before, which shows that the fine scale smoothing dramatically improve the limiting accuracy of the solution. Interestingly, the rate of convergence is similar for the first few cycles compared to the case of exclusively using coarse solves in the previous section. However, the convergence does bottom out abruptly after the second cycle. The third row of plots in Figure 8 separately shows the error within the interior of the domain and the total error, which shows that the interior error fluctuates without affecting the total error. While numerical precision contributes to this issue, this also suggests that solves on the coarse mesh improve interior nodes while also negatively impacting the error along the boundary. It is therefore possible that better handling of the boundary could further improve the asymptotic level of convergence. Further simulations have also shown that the asymptotic convergence level is sensitive to the details of the patch layout in ways that are not yet fully

clear. However, we anticipate being able to reduce the asymptotic error significantly further.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have implemented a novel multigrid technique which takes influence from a variety of existing multiscale methods to enable rapid solution of complex multiscale nonlinear problems. In principle, it can be applied directly to any nonlinear phenomenon for which we can model the fine scale behavior. We have demonstrated the capacity to solve nonlinear elastic problems to well below the error level of a coarse mesh using solely coarse solves and patch-local smoothing. Interestingly, the nonlinear and linear cases demonstrated similar convergence rates and asymptotic levels. As this study considered only geometrically nonlinear hyperelasticity, which is smooth in nature, it remains to be seen whether more complex nonlinearity, particularly highly localized nonlinearity such as cohesive fracture, exhibits a similar behavior.

Moving forward, we are prioritizing transitioning the implementation to GPUs. This will be simplified greatly by the fact that the current implementation is built in JAX, which can be adapted to GPUs nearly transparently. The GPU transition will allow for significant scaleup in feasible problem size, allowing for the exploration of larger meshes, deeper mesh hierarchies, and three-dimensional domains. The other main priority is expanding the breadth of physical phenomena under consideration, especially incorporating fracture. As noted above, this only requires implementing the fine scale model of these phenomena in our JAX-based framework, as the coarser levels incorporate the nonlinear physics through the Taylor coefficients, independent of the underlying mechanisms.

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